

Artificial Intelligence and Medical Liability in Gastrointestinal Endoscopy

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Integrating artificial intelligence (AI) in gastrointestinal (GI) endoscopy signifies a critical advancement for gastroenterology practice. Algorithms for computer-aided detection (CADe) of colorectal polyps have already been introduced in routine clinical care, and a wide variety of other AI applications for GI endoscopy are in advanced phases of development. There is particular interest in whether computer-aided diagnosis (CADx) could replace traditional histopathology for diagnosing small colon polyps, supporting “resect and discard” or “diagnose and leave” strategies.¹ Capsule endoscopy may represent an opportunity for even higher levels of AI automation, including fully automated reporting. Such advancements in AI aim to enhance efficiency, safety, and diagnostic accuracy in GI endoscopy. Nevertheless, errors may still occur when physicians integrate AI into clinical decision-making, sometimes with ensuing liability risk. The degree to which an individual physician or healthcare organization may be legally responsible for an AI algorithm’s error depends on how the tool is integrated into practice and the algorithm’s level of automation. In this article, we delve into the pivotal liability considerations for physicians and healthcare organizations as AI assumes a more prominent role in GI endoscopy clinical practice.

Assistive vs Autonomous AI Algorithms in GI Endoscopy

To explore the legal ramifications of AI algorithms in GI endoscopy, it is first critical to understand the potential range of automation of clinical algorithms from “level 1”, providing limited decision support, to “level 5” or full automation (Supplementary Table 1). In GI endoscopy, the relevant levels of AI automation will differ across potential clinical applications (Figure 1.)

The U.S. Food and Drug Administration has already permitted the marketing of several colon polyp CADe tools, which are examples of “level 1” assistive algorithms. The clinician may respond to or ignore the CADe alert box on the basis of the clinician’s interpretation of whether the alert is

a true positive or a false positive. Enthusiasm toward CADe technology is generally high. However, clinical adoption has been slower than expected, potentially owing to perceived implementation costs among other factors.

The next wave of assistive algorithms in GI endoscopy will likely be “level 2” CADx tools, which provide a prediction of polyp diagnosis, to augment the clinician’s optical diagnosis. In some circumstances, CADx could replace histopathology, supporting a resect and discard or diagnose and leave strategy for small polyps. Potential advantages of these approaches include avoiding unnecessary polypectomy and reducing histopathology costs. Still, endoscopist interest in polyp CADx seems lukewarm, with only 57% of gastroenterologists expressing willingness to consider a CADx-supported diagnose and leave strategy for small polyps.² Endoscopists have expressed concerns regarding liability for diagnostic error if they rely on AI/CADx instead of sending tissue for histopathology diagnosis.³

Algorithms with even higher levels of automation may also enter GI endoscopy.⁴ Capsule endoscopy is a particularly appealing target for automation because unlike other forms of endoscopy requiring live interpretation and action, a capsule endoscopy is more akin to radiology tasks, involving delayed review of thousands of still images. Current versions of capsule endoscopy software use a suspected blood indicator to help streamline physician review by highlighting areas of interest. Future AI-driven algorithms may detect and diagnose a much broader range of small bowel pathology, potentially with high levels of algorithmic automation, ranging from preselection of high-value images for physician review to algorithms that complete the entire capsule endoscopy interpretation without clinician confirmation.

Abbreviations used in this paper: AI, artificial intelligence; CADe, computer-aided detection; CADx, computer-aided diagnosis; GI, gastrointestinal.

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Technology	Role/output	Clinical purpose	Automation level and liability considerations
Colon Polyp CADe 	Polyp detection.	Colon polyp CADe is intended to support endoscopists by improving polyp detection and reducing polyp miss rate.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Automation Level 1 Minimal impact on endoscopist liability because this is a Level 1 algorithm that provides additional information that can be evaluated by the endoscopist using their independent medical expertise. If CADe becomes standard of practice, then failure to use CADe may introduce liability.
Colon Polyp CADx 	Polyp diagnosis prediction (e.g., “adenoma” vs “hyperplastic”).	CADx use may support adoption of “resect and discard” or “diagnose and leave” strategies, reducing use of traditional histopathology.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Automation Level 2 Impact on liability depends on the evolution in standards of care around use of CADx and impact on polypectomy strategies. Physicians must ensure that algorithms are used in accordance with manufacturer’s instructions and indications for use.
Automated Capsule Endoscopy Reading 	Range of roles from detecting or highlighting abnormalities for physician reader to fully autonomous completion of report.	Automated capsule reading algorithms are designed to improve efficiency and accuracy of image review, and may enable fully-automated interventions in the future (biopsy, etc.).	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Automation Levels 1–5 Impact on liability depends on the level of automation achieved by automated capsule reading algorithms, and evolving standards of care. Physicians must ensure that algorithms are used in accordance with manufacturer’s instructions and indications for use.

Figure 1. Automation levels and liability considerations for representative AI tools in GI endoscopy. (Illustration by Danielle Duffey).

AI Algorithms and Liability Considerations in GI Endoscopy

Here, we present 2 hypothetical vignettes to explore the liability aspects of using AI systems in GI endoscopy, with a particular emphasis on CADx and automated capsule endoscopy reading.

Vignette 1: Misdiagnosis Colon Polyp—CADx Resect and Discard vs Diagnose and Leave

A 50-year-old patient presents for a screening colonoscopy. An endoscopist identifies two 5- to 8-mm polyps in the sigmoid colon during the colonoscopy. A legally marketed CADx tool provides a hyperplastic diagnosis prediction for both polyps. On the basis of this CADx prediction, which supports the endoscopist’s clinical impression, the endoscopist removes and discards the 8-mm polyp and leaves the 5-mm polyp in place. Follow-up colonoscopy is recommended in 10 years as per clinical guidelines. Seven years later, the patient is

diagnosed with metastatic colon cancer with a primary lesion in the sigmoid colon. A lawsuit against the endoscopist contends that the interval colon cancer was caused by a prior misdiagnosis of the 5-mm polyp and the subsequent failure to remove that polyp, allowing it to grow into a cancer. To support this claim, the patient presents the opinion of an expert medical consultant who reviewed images in the original endoscopy report and opined that the polyp’s surface pattern (NICE class 2) was compatible with an adenoma.

Vignette 2: Missed Diagnosis by Capsule Endoscopy Workflow Tool

After a normal upper endoscopy and colonoscopy, a 60-year-old patient undergoes capsule endoscopy to further evaluate transient melena and anemia at a hospital system that has recently adopted a legally marketed “first-pass review” AI algorithm for capsule endoscopy workflow. The AI system flags all potentially abnormal findings for an endoscopist to review. The AI system

interprets the capsule endoscopy as normal, and the patient is directly informed of this result without an endoscopist's review. Five months later, the patient presented to the emergency department with another episode of bleeding. Imaging reveals a small bowel mass with surrounding lymph nodes, and the patient is taken to surgery, with surgical pathology confirming a diagnosis of small bowel adenocarcinoma. A lawsuit against the hospital contends that the hospital's integration of the AI system in its capsule endoscopy workflow caused the patient to suffer harm and treatment delay from the missed adenocarcinoma.

Liability Considerations

In both vignettes, the patient files a lawsuit claiming harm stemming from using AI in their clinical care. To be successful, the patient would need to prove the 4 main elements of a medical negligence claim: (1) a duty of care, (2) a breach of the duty of care, (3) causation, and (4) damages (Supplementary Figure 1).⁵ In addition, healthcare organizations and individual providers can be liable for injuries caused by the negligence of employees or people over whom they exercise some control, such as physicians and medical trainees. Although medical negligence cases can involve claims against a myriad of defendants, we focus on the direct liability of the endoscopist in Vignette 1 and of the hospital in Vignette 2. We will also assume that the patient suffered damages in both cases.

A Duty of Care

Notably, AI is not a legal person and thus cannot owe patients a duty of care. For manufacturers of AI, liability generally depends on whether there is a defect in the AI's design, manufacture, and marketing.⁵ It is well-settled law that physicians owe a duty of care to their patients to provide treatment in accordance with generally accepted medical standards. Furthermore, hospitals and other healthcare organizations can also have a direct duty of care to patients to provide and maintain proper staff, equipment, facilities, protocols, and procedures.⁵ As a result, the patient can prove that a duty of care existed in both vignettes.

A Breach of the Duty of Care

Generally, expert testimony from a physician practicing in the same field as the defendant must establish the applicable standard of care and a breach of that

standard in medical negligence cases.⁶ Acceptance of both CADE and CADx tools in endoscopy will be impacted by evidence-based standards such as guidelines issued by medical professional societies, regulatory review and marketing authorization of such tools, commonly used reference tools such as UpToDate, and other resources available to healthcare organizations. In addition, as exemplified by LumineticsCore (formerly called IDx-DR), an AI that diagnoses diabetic retinopathy without human supervision, stakeholders such as payors and patients will also impact incorporating CADx tools into the standard of care. For LumineticsCore, its uptake by healthcare providers was likely highly influenced by the fact that payors created the current procedural terminology (CPT) code and that the American Diabetes Association included the autonomous system in its standard of care.⁷

Even if CADx tools for polyp diagnosis and capsule endoscopy are incorporated into the standard of care for endoscopic practice, hospitals and endoscopists must still follow more general standards of care regarding implementing such tools. This can include ensuring that they are used in the correct patient population and by the manufacturer's instructions, maintaining policies for training staff, informing patients, and ensuring that CADx tools are secure, properly functioning, and up to date.⁸

In Vignette 1, the mere use of a legally marketed CADx tool during endoscopy will likely not violate the standard of care unless there is some reason that the use of the CADx for this specific patient would not have been supported by the relevant clinical guidelines and manufacturer's instructions for using the AI at the time of the colonoscopy.⁸ In addition, because the CADx's output supported the endoscopist's clinical impression, there is no reason to believe that the endoscopist should have known that the CADx's "hyperplastic" determination was incorrect. On the other hand, if the endoscopist had a reason to believe that the polyp was an adenoma based on the endoscopist's clinical expertise and failed to investigate that possibility further, this would likely be considered an unreasonable course of action that might breach the standard of care.

Alternatively, if the AI had determined that the 5-mm polyp was an adenoma during the colonoscopy and the endoscopist overruled that determination using the endoscopist's own clinical experience to diagnose the lesion as hyperplastic, the endoscopist's misdiagnosis might be considered to breach the standard of care because the patient might argue that the endoscopist should have known (because any reasonable endoscopist in her field would have known) that the polyp was potentially an adenoma based on the AI's output. Still, the endoscopist may explain the clinical decision to

ignore the AI's recommendation in a way that still complies with the standard of care.

In Vignette 2, again the hospital's incorporation of the legally marketed AI into its capsule endoscopy workflow is not likely to breach a standard of care, assuming that it was appropriate to use the AI for its patient population. However, suppose the hospital failed to adequately train its staff regarding proper use of the AI, failed to monitor or update the AI system, or otherwise failed to implement and follow protocols related to the safe use of the AI system for capsule endoscopy review. In that case, the patient may be able to establish a breach of the standard of care.⁸ For example, if the hospital fails to implement or follow a procedure for confirming the capsule endoscopy images/video quality before using the AI tool, the hospital may be liable if low-quality images contributed to the AI's false-negative finding.

Causation

Expert testimony is also generally required to establish that the patient's harm was caused by the defendant's breach of the standard of care in medical negligence cases.⁶ Proving causation can be challenging in medical negligence cases because it can be difficult to determine whether the breach, rather than the patient's preexisting medical condition, caused harm. Notably, in the United States, if a defendant's breach of the standard of care increases the plaintiff's preexisting health risks, it will likely still be considered a cause of an injury that stems from those risks.⁹ On the other hand, if the injury that manifests is too far removed from what is reasonably foreseeable because of the defendant's breach, the patient may not be able to prove causation.¹⁰

In Vignette 1, the patient would first have to prove that the adenoma was not a new interval lesion but a preexisting lesion misdiagnosed during the prior colonoscopy. Second, because the endoscopist used their clinical expertise to determine that the polyp was hyperplastic, the AI's hyperplastic determination will likely not affect causation in this case. In other words, if the AI is removed from the course of events, there would likely be no change in the endoscopist's decision and the patient's subsequent clinical outcome.

In Vignette 2, the patient would need to prove that the hospital's decision to use the AI in this case, assuming that the decision breached the duty of care, caused or significantly contributed to the patient's harm from the missed adenocarcinoma. This may be possible if an

expert medical consultant reviews the capsule endoscopy and opines that it contained abnormalities that a human endoscopist should have noticed, and further that these abnormalities would have led to steps that would have improved the patient's outcome.

Conclusion

When an adverse outcome occurs during patient care, the use of an AI algorithm may raise important questions about whether its use generally and the circumstances surrounding its use for each patient specifically breach the applicable standard of care. The answer to these questions will largely depend on whether and how such tools become part of the standard of care based on practice guidelines and routine clinical use by many practicing endoscopists.⁵ Successful integration of polyp CAdE/CADx, automated capsule endoscopy reading, and a wide variety of other algorithms into GI endoscopy will require the collaboration of all stakeholders to ensure that these tools are safe, properly implemented, and monitored. During this process, hospitals, medical groups, and gastroenterologists considering AI-driven tools should carefully consider when and how these tools should be adopted. Specialty societies and health-care organizations should develop guidelines around physician oversight for AI tools at various levels of automation. For physicians, thoughtful clinical documentation, regardless of whether they follow or ignore AI recommendations, remains central to minimizing liability risks.⁸

Supplementary Material

Note: To access the supplementary material accompanying this article, visit the online version of *Clinical Gastroenterology and Hepatology* at www.cghjournal.org, and at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cgh.2024.03.011>.

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Conflicts of interest

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Supplementary Figure 1. The 4 main elements of a medical negligence claim: (1) a duty of care, (2) a breach of the duty of care, (3) causation, and (4) damages. (Illustration by Danielle Duffey).

Supplementary Table 1. Levels of AI Automation

Level of automation	Description	Clinical example
Level 1	Data presentation	Computer-aided polyp detection
Level 2	Decision support with final decision made by clinician	Computer-aided polyp diagnosis
Level 3	Conditional partial automation requiring final clinician review and approval	Capsule endoscopy with automated report requiring clinician review and approval
Level 4	High automation with no intended backup by clinician under most conditions	Capsule endoscopy with automated report completed with optional clinician review (eg, for high-risk finding)
Level 5	Full automation with no role for clinician under any condition	Capsule endoscopy with automated report completed with no clinician review required